

Adapting healthy literacy diet plan as supplementary approach in vocabulary development among selected grade 7 students of Mariano Marcos Memorial High School

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Abstract

Dependent readers often read less, have less exposure to print and therefore have limited sight vocabularies (Rief & Stern, 2010). In this study, the researchers examined effectiveness of adapting healthy literacy diet plan as supplementary approach in vocabulary development. The study targeted a group of 55 identified dependent readers among selected grade 7 students of Mariano Marcos Memorial High School. The intervention consisted of two treatments; treatment 1 was for twenty-three (23) dependent readers who used the diet literacy plan and treatment 2 was for twenty-two (22) identified dependent readers who used traditional vocabulary activities. Based on the findings, the researchers found out that adapting the modified model was effective in treatment 1. The score increased from means of 9.17 to 37.17, signifying a 72.23% improvement percentage rate. In Treatment 2, the score increased from means of 9.0 to 32.5, signifying a 52.22% improvement percentage rate. As compared both post-test results of each group signify that treatment 1 who used the healthy literacy model resulted to 10.40% higher compared to the group who did not utilize the model. The comparison of the two treatments determined the significant difference using adapted and standardized methods of word reading, reading fluency, reading comprehension, word attack skills and spelling. After six months of utilization, majority of the learners made substantial improvements in reading and reading fluency. Reading comprehension enhancements were more varied with almost a quarter of participants showing remarkable progress, while the remainder recorded considerably fewer notable gains (O'Rourke et al., 2016). The results were very encouraging to the researcher and demonstrated that research validated approaches can help at-stake readers close the gap with their typically developing peers.

Keywords: Literacy; Vocabulary; Diet plan; Level of readers; Dependent readers; Independent readers; Advance readers; Reading and vocabulary developmental approaches.

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Introduction

Based on a news article entitled "*National Literacy Month: UN ranks Filipinos as most literate in Southeast Asia*," literacy, most especially amongst the children and youth, is one of the key factors that determines how well a country progresses in this rapidly changing world. The country said to have a misfortunate reality where some Filipinos, young and old, are still struggling with their literacy skills (The Philippine Star, 2019). These individuals as victims of deprivation in education are not only striving for a living but also the opportunity to grow continuously. That is because they opted to find means to fill their stomach rather than go to school and show progress on their literacy skills.

As teachers, we make decisions on what English Reading Instruction we should use as core strategy and component in teaching the subject and developing the skills as providing the instruction itself. The identified learners with greatest needs require the most effect and accurate action. It is very important to provide support to these learners who are at risk on deficient reading outcomes through working out a blueprint for English reading literacy instructional plan that will improve their reading outcomes (Nel, 2018).

This research aims to enrich students' vocabulary through supplementary activities which is more than a word study. The research would adapt a healthy literacy diet plan which can be used by teachers within mainstream schools, an approach that provides students with opportunities to investigate and understand the patterns in words. The model will be modified by the teacher based on the needs of a student who particularly considered as dependent readers even they are already in the junior high school. While word study is often associated with spelling skills, in the process of learning that spelling patterns exist, students will also learn how to apply this knowledge to decoding, which in turn enhances word reading skills by following a certain vocabulary meal plan such as word sort, speed sort, blind sort and word hunt.

In a regular meal, one must follow the food pyramid diet to keep our healthy and balanced body. Likewise, in a learning setup where a hierarchy of learning target skills under the most essential learning competencies should be followed and students should be assessed correctly to completely gauge the reading outcomes progress in a most reliable manner without giving too much pressure to the e-learners. The proposed teaching innovation strategy follows a learning routine that seems to be normal to them yet developing their learning inclusively via virtual classes unknowingly.

Innovation, Intervention, and Strategy

Most teachers find it difficult to gauge how much a student can learn on a virtual classroom. Likewise, students also had a hard time using their own structured learning strategy to cope up every lesson online. Thus, the illiteracy rate in this time of pandemic has been taught to increase in its highest depth due to reported learning conditions.

Dependent readers often read less, have less exposure to print reading materials and therefore have limited sight vocabularies (Rief & Stern, 2010). The more a student reads, the greater their chances of automatically recognizing frequently occurring words (Allington, 2013; Holliday, 2011; Young et al., 2020). This proposed model or approach will serve as supplementary activities integrated in daily lessons for the identified respondents allowing them to take the exercises in order of (1) sorting words, (2) speed sort-accuracy test, (3) blind sort-context clues, and (4) reading exercises – word hunt. These routines will help them improve their skills in an ample time allotted. The researchers used this teaching innovation strategy to extend more assistance in improving reading skills of identified learners fitted even in a self-paced learning approach.

Research Questions

1. What methods are to be used in conducting healthy literacy plan in connection to students' aptitudes?
2. What are the effects of using a healthy literacy diet plan in an e-learning environment?
3. How does the healthy literacy diet plan improve students' performance in English class?

Scope and Limitation

The study was conducted for the purpose of enriching students' vocabulary through supplementary activities which is more than a word study. Adapting and modifying a healthy literacy diet model was done by the researcher based on the needs of a student who particularly considered as dependent readers even they are in the junior high school. This research aimed to assess the students' learning progress on reading skills, and they should be classified as enhanced learners at the end of the study. This research focused only on dependent learners. Identified independent learners were also given same activity with some modifications so they may be able to enhance their skills even they are not the main respondents.

Due to time constraints, the whole research process took place within six months from first to third quarters of school year 2020-2021, but the researchers decided to continue adapting the literacy diet up to the fourth quarter. The studies were conducted among the identified dependent learners from Grade 7 students (Charity, Excellence, Generosity, Frugality, and Justice sections) who are officially enrolled in a blended learning modality. This research was to develop students' reading skills from becoming dependent readers to independent readers.

Healthy Literacy Model was carefully designed and modified by the researcher with the following target skill inclusions:

- a. Sight vocabulary
- b. Meaningful writing
- c. Oral Language
- d. Phonics and decoding
- e. Reading at the 'just-right' level
- f. Access on provided reading material
- g. Reading Fluency
- h. Developing meaningful writing

The study is limited on the actual data from students' scores from their submitted outputs and reflective sheets. Also, their experience or feedback was also collected to affectively assess their personal thoughts on this model. This project did not cover different learning sites but adapted the system during both learning modalities - synchronous and asynchronous classes. Progress on scores was strictly monitored via Google Classroom.

Research Methodology

Participants

Table 1

Number of respondents / participants per section

Section	Number of Participants	Total Number of Students	Percentage of Identified Dependent Learners
Charity	8	45	17.78%
Excellence	9	45	20%
Frugality	11	45	24.44%
Generosity	12	45	26.67%
Justice	15	45	33.33%
Total	55	225	24.44%

The respondents of the study were identified dependent learners in each handled section from Grade 7 of Mariano Marcos Memorial High School in Academic Year 2020-2021. A total of 55 dependent learners were identified using the standardized test (Pre-Test) on reading comprehension in both learning modalities is on Table 1.

Data Collection

This study was conducted in three stages via activities uploaded in their Google Classroom. The first stage was identifying dependent learners in each section through a pre-test activity. Second was the utilization of the Modified Healthy Literacy Diet Model monitored every week.

For the collection of data, the following instruments and platforms were used. To sum up, the following step-by-step process were done to fully view the effectiveness of the study.

The researcher administered the pre-test to all learners. Students who were in blended learning modality answered the pretest through Google Classroom and students who were under modular modality took it via paper-and-pencil test and submitted via JPEG file through Facebook Messenger.

After identifying, collecting data from pre-test and classifying all the learners based on their scores using the score range below.

DEPENDENT READER	0-15 points
INDEPENDENT READER	16-30 points
ADVANCE READER	31-45 points

The teacher listed down the identified dependent learners all the students in each class answered the prepared activity which is weekly as part of enrichment activity. This will prevent labeling of identified dependent readers as low achieving students.

It includes the following: (1) sorting words, (2) speed sort-accuracy test, (3) blind sort-context clues, and (4) reading exercises – word hunt. Answering all the given healthy literacy activity set in an ample time allotted were strictly monitored and check every week. Those improved readers were given extra activities as necessary using the silent reading approach via Informal Reading Inventory Approach which was usually done in a standard English class.

A total of 20 sets with four (4) exercises each of healthy literacy model were given to students within 20 weeks. Each student made a comprehension progress chart to monitor their reading skills improvement every month based on average monthly scores.

Post-test will be administered to all participants after. Data were collected and interpreted, and results were analyzed using dependent t-test for experimental and control group (pre-post) and independent t-test for two groups (post-post). Amount of change is assessed on the value of the dependent variable from the pre-test to the post-test for each group separately.

Ethical Issues

Students' reading and comprehension skills strengthen their ability in learning, understanding, and applying the concepts. In this study, no students were labelled and identified as dependent readers in the class. All students took the pre-test examination as part of the identifying which students needs improvement as well as strictly monitored without letting the students know that they are classified as dependent readers. No informed consent process in the part of the students since it was preceded as a regular activity for everyone, and confidentiality remains in priority to prevent detriment issues. The goal of focusing on their developmental needs without everyone knowing who the dependent readers and everyone is doing the tasks as part of their weekly activity routines. Progress chart was completely done with the assistance of the parents or guardians.

Due to the observed difficulty on their reading comprehension skills, the researcher used the strategy model to improve their skills in vocabulary, composition writing, and reading comprehension within the framework of in a self-paced learning approach via Google Classroom.

Presentation and Discussion of Findings / Results

To determine how the modified healthy literacy model will improve their reading, vocabulary and comprehension skills, the proposed modified Healthy Literacy Diet Plan for Grade 7 Dependent Readers was adapted and used as the same with the covered learning competencies but categorized in four parts that will be integrated in each day lesson. All the students handled by the teacher will undergo on this activity, but data will be focused on identified dependent readers. Below was the overview of activities or exercises given. All questions will be at least 3-5 items only per category.

Planned Activities

Monday - Word or Concept Sort

Students place words into different categories based on each word's meaning.

Tuesday - Speed Sort

Based on assessment results students are given words to study in order to discover the common attributes.

Wednesday - Blind Sort

This is done through working in partners by spelling the word. Since we are conducting online classes, students will be doing this together with their parents/guardians/relatives or may ask help from a classmate and do it via video call for 5-10 minutes only.

Thursday - Word Hunt (Reading Material Access)

Students will read a story and find words which are unfamiliar to them then will add it to their word sort activity for next Monday's word sort.

Figure 1 Healthy Literacy Diet Plan for Grade 7 Dependent Readers

***Every two (2) months, students should include at least 10-15 of learned words in accomplishing quarterly performance task.

The 55 students who were identified as dependent readers was classified into two (a) experimental group with 23 students and (b) control group with 22 groups. The teacher divided the 55 dependent learners into two groups: experimental group (23 students) and control group with (22 students). Dependent t-test was used to analyze the improvements as compared to their posttest in the two groups. Then, the posttest of these two groups were compared and analyzed using independent t-test to significantly identify the difference between the improved skills of the experimental group.

Figure 2 Treatment 1: Pretest vs. Posttest

Figure 2 shows the progress scores of the experimental group (treatment 1) based on their pre-test and post-test scores with a mean of 9.17 (pre-test) and 37.17 (posttest). A percentage from 20.38% to 82.6% with a difference of 62.22% increase were shown.

Figure 3 Treatment 2: Pretest vs. Posttest

Figure 3 shows the progress scores of the control group (treatment 2) based on their pre-test and post-test scores with a mean of 9.0 (pre-test) and 32.5 (posttest). A percentage from 20% to 82.6% with a difference of 72.22% increase were shown.

Figure 4 Comparison of Scores between Experimental and Control Group: Posttest

Figure 4 shows the score differences of the two groups between their posttest scores with a mean of 37.17 (experimental group) and 32.5 (control group). This means that the experimental group shows a higher mean compared to the control group signifying great improvements using the healthy literacy model.

Table 1

Results comparing pre-test and post-test scores on experimental group on literacy skills progress

	Mean	SD	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df
			Upper	Lower		
Pre-Post	20.67	4.513	-28.645	-27.355	-29.757	-28

N=23

*significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 1 shows that there is significant difference on the improved scores of dependent learners from their pre- test to post-test after using the literacy model.

Table 2

Results comparing pre-test and post-test scores on control group on literacy skills progress

	Mean	SD	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df
			Upper	Lower		
Pre-Post	20.75	4.867	-24.212	-22.788	-22.646	-23.5

N=22

*significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 2 shows that there is significant difference on the improved scores of dependent learners from their pre- test to post-test.

Table 3

T-test results comparing post-test scores of Treatment 1 and 2 on literacy skills progress difference

Treatment	N	Mean	SD	t	df	p
Experimental Group	23	37.17	3.725	2.88	21	.003135
Control Group	22	32.5	3.25			

Table 3 shows that there is significant difference on the improved scores of dependent learners who used the Healthy Diet Literacy Model compared to the Control Group which used regular activities.

Conclusions

This research aimed to enrich students' vocabulary through supplementary activities which is more than a word study but in set and considered as part of students' learning routines. Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that:

- Using the model provides students a clear routine from given activities on improving their reading fluency and comprehension.

- b. Statistically, significant differences were observed in the difference of scores from the following:
1. Experimental group (Pre-Test and Post-Test)
 2. Control group (Pre-Test and Post-Test)
 3. Experimental Group vs. Control Group (Post-Post Test)

Based on the t-test values, the experimental group showed a 10.40% higher rate improvements compared to the control group who answered typical sets of classroom activities.

- c. It has been identified that there is a mean difference of 4.67 Treatment 1 (Experiment Group - 37.17) was higher compared to the Treatment 2 (Control Group - 32.5). Thus, using the healthy literacy model had a significant effect on improving students' literacy skills in reading, vocabulary and writing composition.
- d. In this time of pandemic, working in small groups via virtual with peers having different skills can help them learn from each other. They are eager to learn literacy when they discover that it is useful for exploring the given activities and for communicating with others (Lin, 2001).
- e. Ensuring learners' on how to become a skilled reader and writer is a responsibility assisted by teachers, families, and communities. This study shows that inclusive learning using a modified and structured activities with the help of parents and guardians played a vital role in a continuous development on literacy skills that should be done accordingly especially this time of pandemic where students shifted to a very challenging way of learning.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher found out that adapting Healthy Literacy Diet Plan as supplementary approach in vocabulary development among selected grade 7 students of Mariano Marcos Memorial High School was effective. From treatment 1, score was increased from mean of 9.17 to 37.17, signifying a 72.23% improvement percentage rate.

In treatment 2, score was increased from mean of 9.0 to 32.5, signifying a 52.22% improvement percentage rate. As compared both post-test results of each group signify that treatment 1 who used the healthy literacy model show a 10.40% higher compared to the group who did not utilize the model. These results can be helpful:

- a. as a basis of teachers to ensure that every child should become an improved readers using a variety of teaching strategies and learning supplements.
- b. as a tool to measure the learning progress of the students through their scores in each set of activities given.
- c. as a tool to validate their self-paced learning skills with or without assistance to address their learning needs and capacity.
- d. as guiding principles in establishing learning routines conducive and fit to an e-learning environment.
- e. as great way to promote self-paced and inclusive learning even at home.

To help the increase of effectiveness points in this study, the researchers also recommend the following:

- a. Teachers should consider family background and learner's identity, that is, focus on students' experiences and what assistance they can give to the learners in this type of supplemental approach.
- b. The goal of self-paced learning must be explained well to the learners so they can improve their perspectives on the benefits of achieving learning goals at their own pace.
- c. Teachers may also include the supplemental model approach in a minimal item (i.e., 1-3 words study per day) as a regular learning routines in daily learning plan. This may aid a stronger and continuous learning routines for the students.
- d. Teachers may also integrate learning across curriculum in each activity per model set.
- e. Lastly, educators should design literacy instruction that should focus on basic skills and provide rich, significant, and engaging learning environments supported and applicable to different teaching methods and learning modalities.

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